

Agroforestry and Pillar II

- Pillar II CAP is associated with Rural Development payments partially also paid by the EU Member States.
- Pillar II fosters environment interventions linked to sustainable land management in different agricultural croplands, permanent grasslands and permanent crops) and forest land uses on a voluntary basis to **combat climate change** through mitigation and adaptation interventions, **protect habitats** considering natural or area-specific constraints or areas-specific disadvantages resulting from certain mandatory requirements
- Pillar II fosters social interventions linked to knowledge exchange promoting **advisory** systems as part of the CAP 2023–2027 linked to knowledge exchange social interventions.

Agroforestry environment interventions

Agroforestry practices are recognized as such by the ecoschemes, mainly linked to the two main practices of agroforestry: silvopasture (if they are highly biodiverse) and agrosilvicultural practices linked to the establishment, maintenance and cutting plan of agroforestry systems. However, agroforestry can be part as a practice of the CAP proposed list of ecoschemes linked to different types of sustainable farming and livestock systems. Figure 1 shows the agroforestry ecoscheme interventions linked to the use of landscape features, the promotion of grass cover on permanent crops that can be grazed, the production of berries in forest lands and agroforestry as such linked to silvopasture in Greece and to agrosilviculture in Germany. Countries such as Spain, among others, did not promote agroforestry ecoschemes as they are linked to the Pillar II as seen in the Policy Brief number 11.

Agroforestry and Environment Pillar II interventions

Agroforestry is well promoted as part of the Environment Pillar II interventions as can be seen in Figure 1. The Agroforestry environmental interventions clearly complement or enhance the ecoscheme interventions. Most of the interventions are linked to the South and Central Europe, being the them shortly supported in the east part of Europe. The most promoted activities are recognized as agroforestry as such (silvopasture or agrosilviculture) but it can also be found others linked to honey, hedgerows, grassland, forest, livestock breed promotion or even homegardens that are agroforestry but not recognized as such by the intervention. Therefore, CAP 2023–2027 Pillar II promotes agroforestry across most of the EU countries as appeared in their strategic plans.

FIGURE 1. Agroforestry interventions

However, the name of agroforestry is not extensively used across Europe to identify these techniques. A strategy to set a framework to adequately recognize agroforestry should be promoted

Agroforestry and knowledge exchange

Agroforestry is not clearly recognized as such in the different sections of the CAP. AF4EU Regional Agroforestry Innovation Network results highlighted the need of knowledge exchange to foster agroforestry across Europe. AF4EU developed a set of sections to enhance knowledge linked to the AF4EU-Knowledge Cloud as a searchable reservoir, AF4EU-

FIGURE 2 NUMBER OF OPERATIONAL GROUPS LINKED TO AGROFORESTRY

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MAIN CONCLUSIONS

- **Agroforestry is part of the Rural Development Programme of the CAP 2023-2027 complementing the ecoschemes**
- **Most of the agroforestry ecoschemes are linked to silvopasture and agrisilviculture in agriculture and forest land use systems.**
- **Agroforestry needs a clear strategy based on actors cooperation and knowledge exchange fundamented in powerful and independent advisory systems.**

Alive handbook as a book integrating agroforestry knowledge of three EU projects and AF4EU MOOC for self-learning soft and hard AF skills whose content was based on over 1,700 participants in the RAINs all over Europe. The business models decision support tool developed by AF4EU contributes to the land cohesion as it proposes a multiple use of the territory that needs territory citizens cooperation and therefore revitalizes the EU Rural areas.

AF4EU: a groundbreaking initiative to foster European agroforestry

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